

Novel Stereochemical Features of Some Ni(II) Complexes Involving Sulphur Donor Ligands

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THE variety of stereochemical configurations attained in the complexes of Ni(II) with attendant complications of interconversion of different structures as well as possible equilibria between different geometries obtaining in these complexes, has recently aroused considerable interest in the study of such complexes. A valence bond considerations shows that the free Ni(II) ion ($3d^8$ electron configuration) should have two unpaired electrons in both tetrahedral and octahedral complexes involving sp^3 and sp^3d^2 hybridisations respectively and no unpaired electron in a square planar complex involving dsp^2 hybridisation. Five coordinate complexes of Ni(II) which may be square pyramidal or trigonal bipyramidal may have either two or no unpaired electrons. As against magnetic moment value of 2.83 B.M. corresponding to two unpaired spins, octahedral Ni(II) complexes have been found to exhibit values as high as 3.5 B.M. with all intermediate ones, the increase in magnetic moment being attributed to spin-orbit coupling.¹

These standard correlations between bond type, magnetic moment and structure have not been proved either theoretically by independent energy and bond type calculations or experimentally by proof of structure for pertinent compounds. Harris et al.² (1960) prepared a six coordinate, diamagnetic complex of nickel iodide with orthophenylene bis-dimethyl arsine for which the structure has been determined by X-ray.³ Davison et al.⁴ (1963) synthesised a number of salts of composition $N_4S_4C_4R_4^-$ (where R=Ph, CF_3 , CN) which proved to be planar four coordinated paramagnetic in nature. Magnetic moment values much below 2.83 B.M. for supposedly spin-free complexes and values upto 3 B.M. for supposedly diamagnetic complexes in solution have recently been reported and explained on the basis of configurational equilibria⁵⁻⁹ in solution. Polymeric struc-

tures have also been reported for some nickel complexes formed by infinite chains with various ligands bridging the nickel atoms.¹⁰ The nickel-ethylthiolate complex containing sulphur bridges may be cited as an interesting example.¹¹ Cases of mixed stereochemistry in the crystal have also been reported.^{12,13} We have recently observed lowering in the magnetic moment value much below the value for two spins in the solid state in some complexes of Ni(II) involving sulphur ligands^{14,15,16}. We believe that in these complexes, two nickel atoms, one octahedrally surrounded and the other surrounded by four groups in the same plane, are present in the *same molecule*. This is a rather novel feature of stereochemistry of Ni(II) and it has been supported by electronic spectral data.

The variety of configurations obtained in nickel complexes involving particularly sulphur ligands has relevance, perhaps to the following factors :

(i) Nickel(II) is on the borderline between class a and b metals, displaying mild class b character towards sulphur as a ligand atom and, therefore, having limited tendency towards formation of metal-ligand π -bonds.¹⁷

(ii) No uniform pattern for the donor-acceptor relationship of metal-sulphur link based on electronegativity, the ligational free energy change (ΔG) and the M-S $d\pi-p\pi$ or $d\pi-d\pi$ bonding can yet be evolved.¹⁸ Formally sulphur resembles oxygen, having on the bivalent state two unshared pairs of electrons but the low effective nuclear charge of sulphur results in enhanced strength of both σ and π bonds.¹⁹ It is free from complications of hydrogen bonding but shows increased power of catenation. In certain sulphur compounds, π -bonding is more prominent than that found in similar phosphorus compounds.²⁰ The dependence of trans-effect on the degree of π -bonding, however, seems to give place to

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activation of trans-position due to strong polarizability in sulphur ligands.^{21, 22} Among sulphur donors themselves, those containing -SH group coordinate readily with transition metal ions but sulphides are reluctant to do so. The position of sulphur in the spectrochemical series of ligands is not clear.²³ Sulphur should have high nephelauxetic effect but data are insufficient to ascertain this. Commendable efforts^{24, 25} have been made to rationalise conflicting, and in many cases insufficient data on the coordinating ability of sulphur, but not with much success. Klopman's recent approach²⁶ involving conditions for the total perturbation energy of the "frontier orbitals" when they come closer, would lead to a covalent bonding only by soft-soft interaction but nickel has only very mild b character.

It is not surprising then that a number of review articles^{27, 28, 29, 30} on the stereochemical features of Ni(II) have appeared from time to time. Meriting special mention are the one by Porai-Koshits and Cilinskaia²⁹ (1966) giving an account of X-ray crystallographic work and the other by Sacconi³⁰ (1968) giving a very comprehensive account of the magnetic and spectral data and interpretation thereof in regard to different stereochemistries obtaining in nickel(II) complexes including possible distortions. More relevant in the present context of nickel complexes involving sulphur ligands are the reviews by Jorgensen²⁵, Livingstone¹⁸ and Gray³¹.

In Tables 1, 2 and 3 are listed references to many well characterised Ni(II) complexes involving sulphur donor ligands. Gray³¹ in his recent review has made a striking observation on a molecular orbital approach that all square-planar metal complexes containing ligands with equivalent perpendicular(I) and in-plane π -orbitals are diamagnetic and contain a d^8 central metal ion like Ni(II). This is consistent with the electronic energy level scheme since exactly eight electrons can be accommodated in the relatively stable antibonding orbitals derived from d_{xy} , d_z^2 , d_{xz} and d_{yz} . For stabilizing the planar geometry, therefore, a way should be found to involve the metal p_z valence orbitals in such an extensive π -orbital network that total stabilization would overcome the extra stability gained when the p_z orbital is used to form extra σ bonds with axial groups. They chose a bidentate chelate system like maleonitrile dithiolate (MNT_2^-) and prepared truly planar four coordinated $(CH_3)_4N_2[Ni(MNT)_2]$ as shown by X-ray crystallographic and electronic spectral study. The proof of unusual stability of the basic planar system was provided by Schrauzer and Mayweg³² who

prepared the non-electrolyte diamagnetic complex $[Ni\{S_2C_2(C_6H_5)_2\}_2]$. Toluene 3,4 dithiolate with nickel in ethanol solution yields the complex ion $[NiS_2(C_6H_5CH_3)_2]$ which is paramagnetic with $S = \frac{1}{2}$.

TABLE 1—SOME OCTAHEDRAL COMPLEXES OF Ni(II) WITH SULPHUR DONOR LIGANDS

Ligand	Complex	Reference
Thiourea	$[NiL_4Cl_2]$	37, 38
	$[NiL_2(NCS)_2]$	39
Ethylene thiourea	$[NiL_2(NCS)_2]$	40
	$[NiL_6](ClO_4)_2$	3
	$[NiL_4X_2]$, X = Cl ⁻ , Br ⁻ , I ⁻	
Diethyl thiourea	$[NiL_6](ClO_4)_2$	3
Naphthyl thiourea	$[NiL_4Cl_2]$	3
Thioamino pyridine	$[NiL_3](ClO_4)_2$	41
2-methyl thiomethyl pyridine	$[NiL_2X_2]$, X = Cl ⁻ , Br ⁻ , I ⁻	42
2-methyl thioaniline	$[NiL_2X_2]$, X = Cl ⁻ , Br ⁻ , I ⁻	43
Dimethyl aminoethane thiol	$[Ni_2L_2(OH)_2(H_2O)_4]$	63
	$[Ni_2L_2(NH_3)_2(H_2O)_4]$	
1-phenyl tetrazoline-5-thione	$[NiL_2(py)_2]$	36
Thiosalicylic acid	$H[NiL_2] \cdot 2C_2H_5OH$	44

Since the spectrum of a complex is characteristic of the ground state of metal ions, the essential distinction between paramagnetic and diamagnetic complexes of Ni(II) is the difference in the ground states of the metal ion. The lowest energy state for an octahedral complex is the spin free³ A_{2g} (triplet) whereas the ground state for a square planar complex is the spin paired¹ A_{1g} (singlet). Maki³³ has argued that there is a crossover point at which the two states have equal energy and on either side of this point, Ni(II) ion could have a different ground state. Thus a spin-free square planar complex and a spin-paired distorted octahedral complex are possible. Near the cross-over point, the two ground states may be in thermal equilibrium. This results in an intermediate magnetic moment for the complex. Many four coordinate Ni(II) complexes have been reported³⁴ to exhibit temperature dependent magnetic moments in solution of 0-2 spins.

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TABLE 2—SOME SQUARE PLANAR COMPLEXES OF Ni(II) WITH SULPHUR DONOR LIGANDS

Ligand	Compound	Reference
Thiocarbohydrazide	[NiL ₂]	45
Thio-semicarbazide	[NiL ₂] ₂	46
N-N-diethyl dithiocarbamate	[NiL ₂]	47
N, N-dipropyl dithiocarbamate	[NiL ₂]	48
Biacetyl bis mercapto-alkyliminate	[Ni(bami)]	49
Toluene, 3, 4-dithiol	[NiL ₂] ²⁻ , [NiL ₂]-	31
Maleonitrile dithiol	[NiL ₂] ²⁻ , [NiL ₂]-	49
Diphenyl ethylene dithiol	[NiL ₂] ²⁻ , [NiL ₂]-	31
N-phenyl 2-thiocarbomoyldimedone	[NiL ₂]	50
N-methyl 2-thiocarbomoyl dimedon	[NiL ₂]	50
Mono thio- -diketones*	[NiL ₂]	51, 52, 53, 54, 55

* Other compounds containing the grouping —C(SH)=CHCO— also give square complexes. These are mentioned below :

Ethylthioacetoacetate ; Ehythiobenzoil acetate ; Ethyl 3-(4-nitrophenyl)-3-mercaptopropenoate ; Ethyl 3-(4-methoxyphenyl) ; -3-mercaptopropenoate ; Ethyl O-mercaptobenzoate ; iso-propyl-O-mercaptobenzoate ; iso-Amyl O-mercaptobenzoate ; S-Ethyl O-mercaptothiobenzoate ; S-iso-propyl O-mercaptothiobenzoate ; S-iso-Amyl O-mercaptothiobenzoate ; S-Ethyl B-mercaptothiocinnamate ; S-iso-Propyl B-mercaptothiocinnamate ; S-Benzyl B-mercaptothio-cinnamate ; N-Ethyl B-mercaptocinnamamide ; N-phenyl B-mercapto-cinnamamide ; N-phenyl B-mercaptocinnamamide ; 2-Thioacetylcyclopentanone ; 2-Thioacetylcyclohexanone ; 2-Thioacetylcycloheptanone.

Eaton and coworkers⁶ have argued that the crystal field considerations predict that a square-planar configuration will be in general energetically favoured over a tetrahedral configuration. This advantage can be overridden by either extreme ionicity as in tetrahalides or extreme steric restrictions as in the triphenyl phosphine complexes. When conditions are less extreme, there may be either an equilibrium between square planar and tetrahedral configuration or the molecule may seek to attain the extra exchange energy of a triplet state by assuming an octahedral configuration by solvation or association. Thus Carlin and coworkers³⁵ have found that [Ni(naptu)₂Br₂]

TABLE 3—SOME TETRAHEDRAL COMPLEXES OF Ni(II) WITH SULPHUR DONOR LIGANDS

Ligand	Compound	Reference
2-methyl, 8-methyl thioquinoline	[NiL ₂]	57
Naphthylthiourea	[NiL ₂ Br ₂] [NiL ₂ I ₂]	3
Thiolactum	[NiL ₄](ClO ₄) ₂ [NiL ₄](NO ₃) ₂ [NiL ₂ X ₂], X=Cl-, Br-, I-	58, 59
Some five coordinate complexes of Ni(II) with sulphur donor ligands		
Orthophenylene methyl-thio diphenyl phosphine	[NiL ₃ X] ⁺	60
Tris (orthomethyl thio-phenyl phosphine)	[NiL X] ⁺	61
Bis (orthomethyl thio-phenyl phosphine).	[NiL X ₂]	60
Bis (diphenyl arsinoethyl) sulphide	[NiL I ₂]	30
Diethyl dithiophosphate	[NiL ₂ (py)]*	62
Ethyl Xanthate	[NiL ₂ (py)]*	30

* Only in solution

and [Ni(naptu)₂I₂] are tetrahedral while the chloride complex is octahedral. Further more [Ni(etu)₄Cl₂] is a normal octahedral complex while [Ni(detu)₄Cl₂] exhibits a weak tetragonal field. A rather delicate balance of steric, electronic, association and solvation effects seems to determine the magnetic and spectral properties of Ni(II) complexes.

Even these factors do not seem to hold a complete answer to a still novel stereochemistry which we have observed in some of our newly prepared complexes^{14,15,16} in the solid state, containing two nickel atoms, one octahedrally surrounded and the other surrounded by four groups in the *same molecule*. The ligands used are (i) dimethyl amino ethane thiol hydrochloride, (CH₃)₂ N.CH₂CH₂SH.HCl (DMAET), (ii) thiovanol CH₂(SH)CH(OH)CH₂OH(TV) and (iii) thiopropionic acid (TPA) which are typical sulphur

ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) AND THEIR ASSIGNMENTS

Ni ₂ (DMAET) ₄ (CHCl ₃) ₂	Ni ₂ (TV) ₄ (H ₂ O) ₂ 16.H ₂ O	Ni ₂ (TPA) ₄ (H ₂ O) ₂	Assignments	Stereo-chemistry
17240	17860	18200	³ T _{1g} (F) ← ³ A _{2g}	Octahedral
26315	29850	29600	³ T _{1g} (P) ← ³ A _{2g}	
	24410	24600	¹ B _{2g} ← ¹ A _{1g}	
22810			¹ A _{1g} ← ¹ A _{1g}	Square-planar
18510			¹ B ₁ ← ¹ A ₁	

Magnetic moment values, μ_{eff} (B.M.) at room temperature, are 2.26* 2.42 2.02 for the three complexes respectively.

*(field and temperature dependence checked.)

donors and have recently found use in medicine and industry. The addition of these ligands to Ni(II) solutions at pH 8-12 causes a deep-violet colouration to develop and it is possible to isolate reddish brown complexes in all cases. Subnormal magnetic moment values and characteristic absorption bands assignable to both octahedral and squareplanar geometry in all cases (given below) suggests the simultaneous presence of octahedral and square planar species in the same molecule. The absorption spectra of the Ni-TV complex at different pH values does not show any variation in the position of molar absorption of the bands.

Recently Agrawal and Dixit³⁶ have added a number of compounds to this list using 1-substituted tetrazoline-5-thione as complexing agent for Ni(II). They have adduced very detailed spectral evidence for the simultaneous presence of square planar and octahedral geometry in the same. This leads us to believe that this phenomenon may be of more general occurrence in the solid Ni(II) complexes than has hitherto been observed. Only future studies would resolve this enigma of more and more novel stereochemistries of Ni(II) complexes.

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